

Appendix for APPT 2026 Submission

No Author Given

No Institute Given

1 Causes of Time Gaps and Optimization Motivation

In traditional list scheduling algorithm based on topological sorting, the task scheduling order is predetermined by dependency relationships. Even tasks can be executed in parallel, such parallelism is neglected due to the sorting sequence. This is because tasks scheduled earlier are assigned to processors in advance, which affects the judgment of available computing resources on computing units for subsequent tasks, thereby creating time gaps. We illustrate it with a simple example, as shown in Fig. 1, Tasks A and B can be executed in parallel. However, according to topological sorting, Task A is first scheduled to p_h , at which point $T_{\text{available}}(p_h)$ is updated to 9. The time when predecessor tasks of B are completed and their result is transmitted to p_h is 4. According to the earliest start time formula $\text{EST}(B, p_h) = 9$, Task B is incorrectly scheduled to execute at time 9. In fact, Task B could utilize the time gap $[4, 7]$ on p_h . Such resource idleness caused by topological sorting results in the waste of computing resources. Therefore, it is necessary to design an appropriate gap-filling strategy to utilize the gaps generated during DAG scheduling. Choosing a suitable gap can improve both task completion time and energy consumption.

Fig. 1. Task scheduling example with time gaps

To facilitate the selection of time gaps, we first define $occupy(p_h)$ as a doubly linked list of time intervals sorted by start time. It is used to record the occupied time slots of p_h . Time intervals are inserted into the corresponding positions while maintaining the sorted order. Each node in the linked list has three attributes: $taskId$, $startTime$, $endTime$, which denote the task ID, the AST of the task, and the AFT of the task, respectively. $startTime$ and $endTime$ together form the time interval during which p_h is occupied. When $x_{i,h}^k = 1$, the actual finish time of task v_i^k is $AFT(v_i^k) = AST(v_i^k) + t^{\text{exe}}(v_i^k, p_h)$. The newly occupied time interval $t(v_i^k)$ of p_h needs to be inserted into $occupy(p_h)$ while maintaining the list sorted by start time.

Then, we define the $insert$ operation for $occupy(p_h)$. If the $endTime$ of the tail node of the linked list is less than or equal to $AST(v_i^k)$, $t(v_i^k)$ can be inserted directly after the tail node. Otherwise, traverse backward from the tail node to find the first node whose $endTime$ is less than or equal to $AST(v_i^k)$, insert $t(v_i^k)$ after this node, and update the node pointers accordingly.

With $occupy(p_h)$, the time gaps of the computing unit can be easily obtained. By traversing the linked list, for adjacent nodes $node_i$ and $node_{i+1}$, if $node_i.endTime < node_{i+1}.startTime$, an gap is formed. Let $gap_{h,x} = [node_i.endTime, node_{i+1}.startTime]$ denote the x -th gap of p_h . Accordingly, we define the $find$ operation on $occupy(p_h)$ to return all potential time gaps. Specifically, the $find(readyTime)$ operation traverses the linked list starting from the tail node until $node_i.endTime < readyTime$, and returns all gaps encountered during the traversal. Here, $readyTime$ refers to the latest time by which all predecessor tasks of the current task have been completed and data transmission has finished.

Time Complexity Analysis: For the $insert$ and $find$ operations, in the worst case, it is necessary to traverse backward from the tail node to the head of the linked list, resulting in a time complexity of $O(n)$. However, in practical scheduling scenarios, most insertions occur at the tail, so the actual overhead is close to $O(1)$. For the lookup operation, thanks to the ordered nature of the designed linked list, the traversal can be terminated early by $readyTime$, making the actual complexity much lower than $O(n)$.